

EDUCATION 4.0: TRANSFORMING COMMUNICATION PRACTICES IN CONTEMPORARY SCHOOL SYSTEMS

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Abstract: This study examined how Education 4.0 is transforming communication practices in contemporary school systems in Rivers State. The study was guided by three objectives, three research questions and one null hypothesis. This study adopted descriptive survey research design with a population of 4961. This comprised of 306 lecturers and 4,655 undergraduate students from the Faculty of Education from the two state-owned universities in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 593, this includes 440 undergraduate students obtained using Taro-Yamane's formula while 50% of 306 lecturer was chosen using a non-proportionate sampling technique, yielding 153 lecturers in total. A 40-item self-developed instrument title "Education 4.0: Transforming Communication Practices in Contemporary School Systems Questionnaire (ETCPCSSQ)" served as the tool for data collection. The instrument was properly assessed by three research experts. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot study which was analysed using Cronbach alpha, a composite coefficient of 0.82 was established. Means and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. The z-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses at the significance level of 0.05. The findings revealed, among others, that the use of artificial intelligence, digital communication platforms and the integration of digital tools into the school system improved interactions between school administrators and teachers, made communication within the school system more interactive and student-centered and improved inclusivity in communication. Given these results, the study concluded that it is clear that education 4.0 signifies a radical change in the way that communications and learning are organized in contemporary educational systems. It adopts learner-centered, tech-driven strategies that promote diversity, teamwork, and lifelong learning in place of conventional teacher-centered methods. Based on these, the study recommended among others, that curriculum planners should create and incorporate thorough digital literacy and digital citizenship programmes that equip all participants with the knowledge and abilities to communicate effectively and responsibly within the educational system.

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Introduction

The Fourth Industrial Revolution, or Education 4.0, has drastically changed the educational environment by calling for a move away from traditional pedagogies and toward more dynamic, tech-driven methods. In order to promote cooperation, engagement, and individualized learning, school systems have evolved their communication strategies, which today mostly rely on digital platforms, artificial intelligence (AI), and real-time feedback mechanisms. By placing a strong emphasis on individualized learning, technology integration, and the development of abilities that will be useful in the future, like creativity, teamwork, and digital fluency, this paradigm brings educational methods into line with the expectations of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Parvez, 2024). In contrast to conventional methods, Education 4.0 places a strong emphasis on competency-based education, individualized learning, digital technology integration, and chances for lifelong learning (Hussin, 2018). Flexibility in learning, teamwork, creativity, learner-centered methods, and the application of cutting-edge technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and data analytics to improve knowledge acquisition and skill development are among the fundamental tenets of Education 4.0 (Ally, 2019).

Communication becomes a key component of effective teaching and learning within this dynamic framework. In order to accomplish the objectives of Education 4.0, it not only makes information sharing easier but also encourages teamwork, improves teacher-student connections, and raises engagement (Cowan, 2020). Furthermore, social media, learning management systems, and messaging apps are examples of digital communication tools that have had a big impact on learning outcomes and teacher-student relationships. Research indicates that these tools enhance feedback loops, motivation, and teamwork, but they also bring up problems like digital inequality and distraction (Obasi & Madumere, 2025). By revealing gaps in digital capabilities and forcing schools to reconsider their communication strategies, the COVID-19 epidemic further pushed the adoption of these tools (Timotheou et al., 2023).

Student-centered learning, contextualized instruction, and the use of smart technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) are all highlighted in Education 4.0 (Oliveira et al., 2023). Thanks to these advancements, interactions between teachers, students, and administrators have changed from being static in the classroom to being flexible and adaptable thanks to digital tools.

Notwithstanding these developments, difficulties still exist. Lack of training, worries about data protection, and digital differences

can all impede efficient collaboration. Furthermore, according to Oliveira et al. (2023), the transition to virtual settings may lessen the depth of in-person interactions, affecting social and emotional indicators that are crucial for holistic education. Similar to this, adoption of technology can be seriously hampered by a lack of access to dependable equipment, the internet, and technical help. Even when there are resources accessible, instructors may become frustrated and use them less frequently due to inadequate maintenance or a lack of IT support (Johnson et al., 2016). Additionally, a lot of teachers suffer with inadequate training in digital tools, which hinders their capacity to successfully incorporate technology into the classroom. This involves not being conversant with platforms such as collaborative apps, video conferencing tools, and learning management systems (Kaminskiené et al., 2022).

Investigating how communication practices are changing within school systems and the implications for instructional effectiveness, equality, and student well-being is still vital despite the expanding corpus of literature on Education 4.0. In order to close that gap, this study examines how 4.0 is transforming communication practices in contemporary education systems, providing guidance to educators, legislators, and tech developers who want to create more inclusive and responsive learning environments.

Statement of the Problem

Even with the quick advancement of technology and the increased focus on Education 4.0, many contemporary educational systems continue to have serious communication problems. Face-to-face contacts and administrative circulars are examples of traditional communication strategies that are becoming less and less effective at addressing the demands of learner-centered, digitally driven environments. Although artificial intelligence tools, learning management systems (LMS), and digital platforms are being introduced to improve engagement, their uptake and efficacy vary throughout institutions. Administrators find it difficult to incorporate communication technology into the current school structures, students find it difficult to adjust to new platforms, and teachers frequently lack proper training in digital communication skills.

Furthermore, problems like the digital divide, inadequate infrastructure, and a dearth of inclusive communication techniques may prevent Education 4.0 from reaching its full potential.

These communication breakdowns have a detrimental effect on student engagement, collaborative learning, feedback systems, and inclusion in addition to decreasing the effectiveness of information sharing between educators, students, and administrators. Therefore, an empirical investigation of how Education 4.0 is influencing communication patterns in contemporary school systems, the difficulties faced, and the tactics needed to

maximize communication for better teaching and learning outcomes is urgently needed.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine how Education 4.0 is transforming communication practices in contemporary school systems in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. examine the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in contemporary school systems in Rivers State
2. identify the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings in Rivers State
3. investigate the strategies that can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles in Rivers State

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. How has Education 4.0 influenced communication dynamics in contemporary school systems in Rivers State?
2. What are the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings in Rivers State?
3. What strategies can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

One null hypothesis was tested for the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both lecturers and students on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in contemporary school systems in Rivers State.

Conceptual Clarification

Education 4.0

As a response to the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), education 4.0 focuses on incorporating new technologies like big data, cloud computing, robotics, artificial intelligence (AI), and the Internet of Things (IoT) into instruction. Learner-centered, flexible, and individualized learning replaces traditional teacher-centered approaches, equipping students with digital literacy, problem-solving, creativity, and teamwork (Puncreobutr, 2016; Miranda et al., 2021). To ensure that students are ready for the rapidly evolving demands of the global workforce, Education 4.0 also places a strong emphasis on adaptation and lifelong learning (Salmon, 2019).

Communication Practices in Schools

Information exchange between school stakeholders, such as parents, teachers, students, and administrators, is referred to as communication practices. In the past, schools depended on in-person classroom interactions, circulars, and memoranda. However, social media, learning management systems (LMS), AI-enabled feedback tools, collaborative applications, and other digital platforms have made communication a multi-modal,

technology-driven system as a result of Education 4.0 (Kapasias et al., 2020). According to Crawford and Cifuentes-Faura (2022), feedback systems, inclusive involvement, student engagement, and collaborative learning are all greatly aided by effective communication techniques.

Contemporary Educational Systems

In order to enhance teaching, learning, and administration, contemporary school systems use cutting-edge pedagogies, digital technologies, and international best practices. To fulfill the demands of Education 4.0, these institutions place a strong emphasis on competency-based learning, diversity, international collaboration, and the use of ICT technologies. They abandon rote memorization in favor of strategies that encourage creativity, critical thinking, and practical problem-solving (Redecker, 2020; Schwab, 2017). Thus, contemporary educational systems offer a context in which successful communication techniques are crucial.

Transformation of Communication

The transition from conventional, one-way information exchange to collaborative, digital, and interactive communication methods is referred to as the "transformation of communication." The following characteristics define communication in Education 4.0 contexts: multimodal communication using text, audio, video, and interactive media; real-time feedback systems made possible by AI and LMS platforms; two-way communication

between teachers and students using digital tools; and globalized communication, where teachers and students work together across borders and cultures.

Methodology

In order to investigate how Education 4.0 is transforming communication practices in contemporary school systems, the challenges faced, and the strategies needed to maximize communication for better teaching and learning outcomes in Rivers State, this study adopted a descriptive survey research approach. This design facilitates the collection of thorough data from a carefully chosen sample of responders. Three hundred and six (306) lecturers and four thousand six hundred and fifty-five (4,655) undergraduate students from the Faculty of Education at the two state-owned universities in Rivers State made up the study's population. Using Taro-Yamane's methodology, the sample size for the student was 400. A 10% rate of invalid and non-respondent responses was then added, for a total of 440 respondents.

The sample for this investigation was chosen using the multistage sampling technique. First, the two state-owned universities (RSU and IAUE) were chosen using the stratified sampling technique. Second, five departments—a total of ten departments—were chosen from each university using the purposive sampling technique. Thirdly, two levels were chosen from each department using purposive sampling. Fourth, the students were chosen using the simple random sample technique. Finally, 50%

of the lecturers in the chosen departments were chosen using the non-proportionate sampling technique, yielding 153 lecturers in total. As a result, 593 respondents make up the study's overall sample.

A 40-item self-developed survey with the title "Education 4.0: Transforming Communication Practices in Contemporary School Systems (ETCPCSS)" served as the tool for data collection. The criterion mean of 2.5 is determined by the weighting of the instrument, which is on a 4-point rating scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 2, and Disagree (D) = 1. It consisted of section "A" "B" and "C" as follows: Section "A" - influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in modern school systems; Section "B" - Questions on the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings and Section "C" - Questions on the strategies that can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles. Three

research specialists properly assessed the instrument's face and content validity. To determine the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested using the test-retest method. The reliability coefficient was 0.82 after the trial test results were analyzed using Cronbach alpha. To examine the data gathered, mean and standard deviation were employed to give a broad picture of the respondents' answers to the study questions and z-test was employed to assess the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. With the assistance of two research assistants, 593 of the instruments were administered; 440 of the students' responses came back with 30 invalid responses, whereas the 153 of the lecturer's responses came back fully. Thus, a total of 563 questionnaires was retrieved successfully.

Results

Research Question 1: How has Education 4.0 influenced communication dynamics in modern school systems in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation scores on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in modern school systems in Rivers State

S/ N	ITEMS	Lecture rs (N = 153)	Students (N = 410)	REMARK
		\bar{x} SD	\bar{x} SD	
1	incorporating digital tools (such as virtual classrooms and learning management systems) enhanced communication between your school's teachers and students	3.49 0.94	3.30 0.87	Strongly Agreed

2	influenced your school's teachers' cooperation and information exchange	3.26	0.85	3.0	0.79	Agreed
3	Communication facilitated by technology enhanced communication between teachers and school officials	3.27	0.86	3.2	0.8	Agreed
4	enabled prompt feedback exchanges between educators and learners	3.31	0.88	3.2	0.8	Strongly Agreed
5	Using digital communication tools (including emails, WhatsApp, and school portals) to improve parent-school communication	3.17	0.82	3.10	0.81	Agreed
6.	decreased obstacles to collaboration inside your educational system	3.29	0.87	3.13	0.8	Strongly Agreed
7.	Artificial intelligence (e.g., chatbots, adaptive learning platforms) has affected how students communicate with instructional materials.	3.50	0.95	3.4	0.91	Strongly Agreed
8.	The practices have improved student-centered and participatory communication within the educational system.	3.44	0.92	3.32	0.8	Strongly Agreed
9.	Impacted the cooperation and communication between students in your school?	3.2	0.86	3.24	0.8	Strongly Agreed
10.	Improved communication inclusivity (e.g., reaching students with different backgrounds and needs)	3.26	0.85	3.15	0.81	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.3	0.8	3.2	0.8	Strongly Agreed
		2	8	2	4	Agreed

***key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD =1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75.**

Table 1 above showed the mean scores and standard deviations of both respondents on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in contemporary school systems. Both respondents strongly agreed that incorporating digital tools (such as virtual classrooms and learning management systems) into teaching and learning enhanced communication between teachers and students, influenced teachers'

cooperation and information exchange, enhanced communication between teachers and school officials and enabled prompt feedback exchanges between educators and learners as seen by the grand means of 3.32 and 3.22 and the standard deviations of 0.88 and 0.84, respectively.

Research Question 2: What are the educational settings in Rivers State? challenges of digital communication tools in

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation scores on the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings in Rivers State

S/N	ITEMS	Lecturers (N = 153)		Students (N = 410)		REMARK
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Restricted availability of reliable internet connectivity	3.25	0.85	3.23	0.84	Agreed
2	Expensive equipment and data	3.31	0.88	3.30	0.88	Strongly Agreed
3	Insufficient training for instructors and lecturers	3.26	0.85	3.20	0.84	Agreed
4	Regular power outages (problems with electricity)	3.30	0.88	3.29	0.87	Strongly Agreed
5	Insufficient institutional support, such as technical assistance or ICT infrastructure	3.20	0.83	3.17	0.82	Agreed
6.	Students' inadequate proficiency in digital literacy	3.36	0.89	3.14	0.81	Agreed
7.	Sometimes an over-reliance on digital communication methods results in less in-person engagement, which weakens interpersonal ties.	2.90	0.75	3.0	0.78	Agreed
8.	Data security and privacy concerns	3.45	0.92	3.24	0.84	Agreed
9.	Technical issues (such as software bugs or system crashes) make it difficult to communicate effectively in a classroom setting.	3.17	0.82	3.06	0.78	Agreed
10.	Digital communication tools are applied inconsistently in schools due to a lack of clear policies and guidelines.	2.84	0.76	2.72	0.74	Agreed
Grand Mean		3.2	0.84	3.1	0.82	Agreed
		0		4		

***key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD = 1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75. n = 563**

Table 2 above, displayed the mean scores and standard deviations of both respondents on the challenges of using digital communication tools in educational settings. Both respondents

agreed with a grand means of 3.20, 3.14 and standard deviations of 0.84, 0.82., that the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings include restricted

availability of reliable internet connectivity, expensive equipment and data, insufficient training for instructors and lecturers, regular power outages (problems with electricity, insufficient institutional support, such as technical assistance or ICT infrastructure

frequent power outages and as well as students' inadequate proficiency in digital literacy skills.

Research Question 3: What strategies can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation scores on the strategies that can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles Rivers State

S/N	ITEMS	Lecturers (N = 153)		Students (N = 410)		REMARK
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
1	Regularly giving teachers and students ICT training	3.34	0.89	3.31	0.88	Strongly Agreed
2	To improve digital communication, schools should make investments in dependable internet connectivity.	3.22	0.84	3.26	0.85	Agreed
3	Clearly defining rules and regulations for digital communication	3.30	0.88	2.90	0.75	Agreed
4	Including digital literacy and communication skills in the curriculum	3.53	0.96	3.40	0.91	Strongly Agreed
5	Building virtual platforms (such as portals, apps, and online forums)	3.13	0.80	3.20	0.84	Agreed
6.	Frequent feedback systems (such as online polls and surveys)	3.21	0.83	3.12	0.79	Agreed
7.	Increasing cooperation between ICT suppliers and schools	2.98	0.78	3.02	0.77	Agreed
8.	Promoting mixed learning, which combines in-person and online interactions	3.40	0.91	3.36	0.89	Strongly Agreed
9.	Enough money should be allocated by the government and school administration to support communication technologies.	3.61	0.99	3.50	0.95	Strongly Agreed
10.	Forming online communities for teachers to engage in professional learning.	3.35	0.90	3.26	0.85	Strongly Agreed

Grand Mean

**3.31 0.8 3.23 0.8 Strongly
 8 5 Agreed**

***key: SA = 3.26-4.00, A = 2.51-3.25, SD =1.76-2.50, D = 1.00-1.75.**

n =563

Table 3 above, displayed the mean scores and standard deviations of both respondents on the strategies that can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles. Both respondents strongly agreed with a grand means of 3.31, 3.23 and standard deviations of 0.88, 0.85., which revealed that regular ICT training for teachers and students, investing in dependable internet connectivity, establishing clear policies and guidelines on digital communication, incorporating digital

literacy and communication skills into the curriculum, and enhancing collaboration between schools and ICT providers are some strategies that can be implemented to strengthen communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles.

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of both lecturers and students on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in modern school systems in Rivers State

Table 4: Z-test analysis showing no significant difference in the mean scores of both lecturers and students on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in modern school systems in Rivers State

Respondents	N	X̄	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
Lecturers	153	3.32	0.88	0.05				Accepted.
					561	1.21	±1.96	
Students	410	3.22	0.84					

Table 4 above displays the analysis of Z-test on the significant difference in the mean scores of both lecturers and students on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in contemporary school systems in Rivers State. The table revealed that the z-calculated value of 1.21 is less than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (561) at 0.05 significant levels. This suggests that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of both respondents on the influence of Education 4.0 on communication dynamics in contemporary

school systems in Rivers State. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is thus accepted while the alternate is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the first research question showed that the use of artificial intelligence (e.g., chatbots, adaptive learning platforms), teacher collaboration and information sharing, digital communication platforms (e.g., emails, WhatsApp, school portals), and other digital tools (e.g., learning management systems, virtual classrooms) improved interactions

between teachers and school administrators, facilitated timely feedback between teachers and students, decreased barriers to communication within the school system, strengthened communication between schools and parents, influenced communication between students and educational content, made communication in the school system more interactive and student-centered, influenced peer-to-peer (student-to-student) communication and collaboration within the school system, and improved inclusivity in communication (e.g., reaching students with diverse needs and backgrounds). These results validate Parvez's (2024) perspective who discovered that the education 4.0 paradigm, which emphasizes individualized learning, technology integration, and the development of skills like creativity, teamwork, and digital fluency, matches educational practices with the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The study's results also support those of Cowan (2020), who believes that digital communication is crucial to accomplishing the objectives of Education 4.0 because it not only makes knowledge sharing easier but also encourages collaboration, improves teacher-student relationships, and increases engagement.

The study also discovered that on the challenges of digital communication tools in educational settings both respondents agreed that restricted availability of reliable internet connectivity, expensive equipment and data, insufficient training for instructors and lecturers, regular

power outages, concerns about privacy and data security, insufficient institutional support, such as technical assistance or ICT infrastructure, students' inadequate proficiency in digital literacy affect the willingness of lecturers/students to fully adopt digital communication platforms, technical glitches (e.g., software errors, system crashes) disrupt effective communication in the learning environment, limited digital literacy skills and absence of clear policies and guidelines on the use of digital communication tools creates inconsistency in its application in schools. This finding is consistent with Johnson et al. (2016), who believe that even in cases when digital communication tools are accessible, teachers may become frustrated and use them less frequently due to inadequate maintenance or a lack of IT support. Similarly, Kaminskienė et al. (2022) discovered that many teachers struggle with inadequate training in digital technologies, which hinders their ability to successfully integrate technology into their lessons. This includes not being comfortable with collaboration apps, video conferencing tools, and learning management systems. He continued by saying that there may be a digital divide that impacts communication and learning results since students from underprivileged communities might not have access to devices or reliable internet (Kaminskienė et al., 2022).

The results in research question three revealed that both respondents strongly agreed that

providing regularly giving teachers and students ICT training, if used to improve communication practices in schools for better alignment with Education 4.0 principles, strategies like investing in dependable internet connectivity, creating clear policies and guidelines on digital communication, integrating digital literacy and communication skills into the curriculum, and enhancing cooperation between schools and ICT providers can all lead to more fruitful interactions. These results are in line with those of González-Pérez & Ramírez-Montoya (2022), who proposed that education programs for parents, students, and instructors guarantee efficient use of communication tools. In addition to promoting fair access to educational materials, this lessens the digital divide. Likewise, the results support Delos Santos's (2025) claim that preparing kids for school involves teaching them how to interact in digital settings, such as email etiquette, virtual presentations, and online cooperation. 4.0 demands

Conclusion

It is clear from the study's results and the in-depth discussion that education 4.0 signifies a radical change in the way that communications and learning are organized in contemporary educational systems. It adopts learner-centered, tech-driven strategies that promote diversity, teamwork, and lifelong learning in place of conventional teacher-centered methods. Redefining communication practices to shift from linear, one-way information sharing to

dynamic, interactive, multimodal communication made possible by digital technologies is one of the most important parts of this shift. The digital gap, poor infrastructure, a lack of teacher preparation, and reluctance to use new technologies, however, continue to be major obstacles in spite of the benefits. Building better relationships between educators, parents, administrators, and students is essential to raising engagement and improving learning results. Communication strategies need to be purposefully adjusted to meet the demands of 21st-century learners and the reality of contemporary school systems if Education 4.0 is to realize its full potential.

Recommendations

1. Comprehensive digital literacy and digital citizenship programs that equip all participants with the abilities to communicate effectively and ethically within the school system should be created and incorporated by curriculum planners.
2. To guarantee ethical and efficient use of technology, schools should give priority to training instructors and students in digital citizenship and communication.
3. To reduce the digital divide, governments and school administration should make investments in cloud computing platforms, modern communication tools, and reasonably priced, dependable internet connection.
4. To improve inclusivity and accommodate a range of learning demands, schools should implement multimodal communication

technologies that enable text, audio, video, and interactive media.

5. To give prompt feedback and promote interactive connection with students and parents, educators should make use of LMS platforms, smartphone apps, and AI-powered technologies.

6. Clear rules that support equity, stimulate the integration of Education 4.0 principles, and address ethical issues like data privacy and accessibility must be developed by educational officials.

7. Schools should support cross-cultural digital partnerships that link students around the world, improving their intercultural competency and communication abilities.

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